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RESEARCH AND SYSTEMATIZATION OF SPECIFIC EXPRESSIONS OF THE ADAPTATION OF RETAIL TRADE ENTERPRISE

Об'єктом дослідження є процес систематизації видових проявів адаптації підприємства роздрібною торгівлі. Оперативність реакції підприємства роздрібною торгівлі на різного роду зміни зовнішнього середовища вимагає гнучкості і адаптивності в прийнятті різних управлінських рішень та визначається його адаптаційним потенціалом. Одним з найбільш проблемних місць є ідентифікація специфічних для підприємств сфери торгівлі видів адаптації. Систематизація видових проявів адаптації підприємства ускладнена відсутністю в економічній літературі єдиного погляду, що гальмує процес формування ефективної адаптаційної політики на торговельних підприємствах.

Проведено аналіз існуючих підходів до класифікації видів адаптації. Визначено основні акценти адаптації підприємницьких структур. Систематизовано та охарактеризовано основні видові прояви адаптації підприємства. Розширено критеріальні ознаки адаптації підприємства шляхом введення додаткових: за рівнем і ступенем планування, за необхідністю інвестиційної підтримки та за ступенем окупності витрат на адаптацію. В ході дослідження визначено характерні особливості адаптаційного потенціалу підприємств галузі роздрібною торгівлі від підприємств інших галузей економіки: чутливість до мінливості вхідних ресурсів та вимог і запитів споживачів.

Визначено структуру маркетингової адаптації підприємства роздрібною торгівлі та виділені товарна, цінова, просторова та комунікаційна види маркетингової адаптації підприємства роздрібною торгівлі з урахуванням їх галузевої специфіки. Ці види адаптації дозволяють торговельному підприємству більш обгрунтовано визначити комплекс адаптаційних рішень, реалізація яких забезпечує адекватність і можливість адаптації підприємства роздрібною торгівлі до умов ринкового попиту, вимог та запитів споживачів. Для визначення базових напрямків маркетингової адаптації підприємства роздрібною торгівлі визначено ключові характеристики елементів комплексу маркетингу «4P». У порівнянні з існуючими підходами до класифікації, запропонована структуризація маркетингової адаптації підприємства роздрібною торгівлі створює можливість відповідати вимогам та запитам споживачів та формувати позитивний споживчий настрій. Здійснення маркетингової адаптації, відповідно елементів комплексу маркетингу «4P», сприятиме зростанню основних результуючих показників діяльності підприємства роздрібною торгівлі.

Ключові слова: адаптація торговельного підприємства, економічна адаптивність, адаптаційний потенціал, адаптивна реакція, адаптивна політика.

1. Introduction

Current economic conditions require from business entities an adequate response to changes in the external environment. At the same time, the stability of the adaptation potential is an obligatory and dominant resource for ensuring timely response of business entities to rapid changes in the external environment. Prompt response of a retailer to various kinds of changes in a wide range of environmental factors requires flexibility and adaptability in making various management decisions. The adaptation potential acquires particular importance in the case of stochastic changes in the economic and market environment during a crisis. From what specific manifestations of adaptation characteristic of a particular retailer depends on the speed and adequacy of the company's response to changes in the external environment.

The recent interest in solving the issues of research on the specific manifestations of the adaptation of a retail enterprise to the external environment is due to the fact that the main characteristics of the modern external envi-

ronment are complexity, uncertainty and dynamism. The changes that occur in the modern external environment are in most unique and require non-standard approaches to solving a particular situation. The above actualizes the issue of search and identification of new and development of existing types of adaptation. Systematization of possible specific manifestations of adaptation will allow to provide a qualitative assessment of the adaptation potential of a retail outlet and to form an effective adaptation strategy. Thus, research aimed at resolving the issues of classification of specific manifestations of the adaptation of a retail enterprise is undoubtedly relevant and requires further scientific research.

2. The object of research and its technological audit

The object of research is the process of systematization of specific manifestations of the retailer adaptation. The adaptation of the activities of any retail enterprise to changes in environmental factors necessitates the implementation

of certain changes in business processes that are characterized by a unique model of adaptation to changes in the external environment. Making a transition to a qualitatively new level of development or, on the contrary, finding themselves in a situation, the business processes of a retail enterprise require a corresponding change in goals, strategies and methods for their implementation. Determining the type of adaptation will allow managers of trading enterprises to make informed management decisions in the future. The adaptation management process should be considered as part of the overall management system of the trading enterprise. Since, with an increase in the intensity of the impact of environmental factors, it is necessary to understand the nature, scale of changes, the specific resources that the merchant needs to «adapt» to them. In this aspect, the lack of information about the possibility of adaptation in the context of certain aspects of the retail trade enterprise activity can adversely affect the overall performance of its activities and competitiveness.

So, a fundamentally important issue of scientific research is the study, clarification and expansion of the classification characteristics of specific manifestations of the adaptation of a retail outlet and the determination of their substantial characteristics. This problem is not enough illuminated in modern economic literature, expands the field of scientific research in this direction.

3. The aim and objectives of research

The aim of research is studying the approaches to the classification of typical manifestations of adaptation, their refinement and expansion of the criteria characteristics of adaptation, taking into account the sectoral specifics of trade enterprises.

To achieve the aim of research the following objectives are defined:

1. To analyze the existing approaches to the classification of the main species manifestations of the adaptation of the enterprise.
2. To expand the classification characteristics of types of adaptation by introducing additional ones.
3. To select specific types of marketing adaptation of the retailer.

4. Research of existing solutions of the problem

The study of the theoretical aspects of the adaptation of the enterprise and its specific manifestations are devoted to the work of many scientists. In these works, various approaches to the classification of types of adaptation of an enterprise depending on the scope of its implementation are considered. So, in works [1, 2], attention is focused on the management adaptation of the enterprise. The author of the work [3] notes that a key aspect of managerial adaptation is the analysis of the organizational structure of enterprise management and the need to ensure its compliance with certain strategic goals and objectives.

Taking into account the various types of adaptive response of an enterprise to changes in the external environment, the author [1] identifies the following types of adaptation: elastic, flexible, plastic. Elastic adaptation is characterized by the fact that as a result of adaptation, the existing basic characteristics of the enterprise remain

unchanged. Flexible adaptation is associated with a change at the time of the structural characteristics of the enterprise with the subsequent return to their original state. Plastic adaptation causes irreversible structural changes in the enterprise.

Special attention is paid to the need for economic adaptation by the enterprise. The most convincing evidence is given in [4]. According to the results of these studies, it is established that economic adaptability covers all key processes of the enterprise. Economic adaptation is aimed at ensuring the dynamic development of the enterprise and optimizing the indicators of its financial condition.

In the works [2, 5], the authors systematize the specific manifestations of adaptation depending on the sphere of operation of the enterprise. In these works, the following types of adaptation will be highlighted: production, marketing, logistics, financial, scientific and technical, and personnel adaptation. The authors believe that each of the mentioned types of adaptation characterizes the ability of an enterprise to adapt to changes in the internal and external environment in the plane of a particular area of its operation.

It is worth noting that in [6, 7] an approach to the consideration of adaptation depending on the temporal characteristic is proposed. According to this approach, the authors identify the following types of adaptation: strategic, tactical, operational [6], permanent, cyclical, periodic, one-moment, long-term, short-term [7]. The author of [8] believes that the choice of the type of adaptation depending on the time characteristic is due to such a characteristic of the environment as variability, that is, the higher the rate of change, the more often the enterprise is forced to turn to the adaptation mechanism.

In [9], the author systematizes the specific manifestations of the adaptation of an enterprise according to the degree and effectiveness of the use of means of production. The research results allowed to distinguish intensive, extensive and integrated adaptation. Extensive adaptation implies a change in the quantity and concentration of the means of production used, which are involved in the adaptation process. Intensive takes into account a better and more optimal use of available means of adaptation, and integrated – involves changes in the use of funds available at the enterprise in other ways in order to bring the activity in accordance with the external environment.

Focusing on the different ways of working in [9], it is proposed to highlight the static and dynamic adaptation of the enterprise. Static adaptation implies the existence in the enterprise of already acquired properties with the help of which the enterprise has adapted to the external environment. Dynamic adaptation is the process of interaction of an enterprise with environmental factors, aimed at adapting to it in the process of doing business. The author of [10] expands the characteristics of dynamic adaptation and highlights such a characteristic feature as the formation of properties that ensure and accelerate the adaptation of an enterprise to changes in the external environment.

The team of authors [11, 12] distinguishes the species-related adaptations depending on the degree of coverage. According to certain classification features, the authors distinguish between local and complex adaptation. When it comes to local adaptation, it means the use of adaptation management tools for the level of individual units. At the same time, when it comes to complex adaptation,

let's mean adaptation at the enterprise level, which covers the entire functional multidimensionality of activity [13].

In order to find effective directions for changing various aspects of an enterprise's activity, the author of [14] classifies types of adaptation depending on the nature of parameter changes, namely: parametric, resource, algorithmic and structural. Parametric adaptation covers changes during the operation of the enterprise, which can be implemented using a simulation approach or neural networks. Resource adaptation is aimed at optimizing the use of resources of the economic system (enterprise) and its individual components (elements). Algorithmic adaptation is associated with the transition from one to another algorithm of enterprise management. Structural adaptation implies a change in the structure of the control system or the structure of the objects being modeled. The author notes that structural adaptation can be of two types: alternative, which implies the existence of several alternatives for choice, and evolutionary, based on minor gradual changes in the structure.

There are approaches to the identification of types of adaptation, depending on the degree of predictability of changes in the external environment. In [15], the author identifies a forced, planned, precautionary adaptation of the enterprise. Forced adaptation occurs when changes in the external environment are unexpected for the enterprise. Planned adaptation occurs when an enterprise has information in advance and expects certain changes in the external environment. Preventive adaptation is carried out by an enterprise with the goal of ensuring sustainable development.

The approach proposed in [16, 17] for the classification of types of adaptation of an enterprise is determined by the nature of changes in the activity of the enterprise. According to this approach, passive, active, moderately active, preventive and compensatory types of adaptation are distinguished.

In [10], active adaptation is aimed at creating favorable conditions for the functioning of the enterprise, passive – is characterized as a change in the behavior of the socio-economic system to ensure more efficient functioning in the environment. Moderately active adaptation implies a set of limited measures to influence individual elements of the environment [16]. The author of [7] notes that the passive type of adaptation is optimal in conditions when an enterprise can't independently influence the environment, for example, in the conditions of the global financial crisis. In [16], preventive adaptation is considered as a change in the functioning of enterprises based on forecasts of environmental changes and intuitive considerations of top managers about promising areas of activity. According to the authors of [17], compensatory adaptation is such forms of adaptation to environmental conditions that occur due to the switching mechanism of the complementary modes of functioning of the adaptation subject.

So, the main approaches to the classification of specific manifestations of adaptation in enterprises are considered, the main types of adaptation of enterprises to changes in the external environment have been characterized. But they did not receive sufficient coverage and require a constructive resolution of a number of issues related to the systematization of the main criterial signs of typical manifestations of adaptation, taking into account the sectoral specifics of trade enterprises. They acquire particular

urgency with increased instability, increased dynamism and complication of the external environment of functioning of trade enterprises in Ukraine.

5. Methods of research

During the execution of the work applied general scientific and special research methods:

- methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, structuring, systematization and generalization – for the classification of specific manifestations of adaptation, determining the content and characteristics of the adaptation of commercial enterprises;
- decomposition method – to determine the main types of adaptation of a retailer to changes in the external environment according to classification criteria;
- comparable comparisons – to characterize individual specific manifestations of the adaptation of a retailer.

6. Research results

It should be noted once more that the performance of any enterprise, its level of competitiveness, further growth and development in the long term are provided, above all, with the ability to carry out timely adaptation to the external environment. Adaptation is the process of adapting an enterprise to the conditions of the external and internal environment, based on the assessment of all subjective-objective factors of enterprise development and aims to ensure its strategic competitive functioning [17]. The goal of an adaptive enterprise management process is, on the one hand, bringing the internal environment in line with external factors, and on the other hand, creation of the ability of an enterprise to resist and influence external factors with possible subsequent environmental changes [18]. The high level of adaptability of the enterprise allows timely warning (or weakening) the effect of threats generated by the external environment, creating prerequisites for further sustainable and balanced development of the enterprise.

The complexity of the adaptation process is explained by the fact that each object at different times can be in different states: $S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_n$. Accordingly, different states are also characteristic of the external environment at different times: $G_2, G_3, \dots, G_n$. Each of the states S and G can be characterized through a system of separate particular indicators:

$$S_i = f(a_i, b_i, c_i, \dots) \text{ and } G_i = f(\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \dots).$$

Both the object and the external environment can be characterized from two points of view:

- state of the system at a certain point in time;
- changes that have occurred in the system for a certain period of time.

It should be noted that the state of the system at a certain point in time is determined by two parameters:

- 1) adaptation environment (a complex of external conditions and factors at a certain point in time);
- 2) sensitivity of the system to changes (the degree of dependence of the enterprise on changes in the external environment).

In turn, the adaptability of the enterprise potential characterizes the nature of changes that have occurred in

the system over a certain period of time. Accordingly, the higher the level of adaptability of the enterprise potential, the less sensitive the enterprise is to changes in the external environment. In the process of building-up the parameters of the internal environment of the enterprise for changes that occurred in the system over time, an adaptive response to an external influence characterizing the adaptability of the enterprise is produced. The adaptive capacity of the enterprise is a characteristic of the ability to change in a particular situation. A wide range of environmental factors, under the influence of which the internal environment of the enterprise changes, leads to the need to identify various types of adaptation in order to develop effective adaptation solutions aimed at improving the adaptability of the enterprise to environmental conditions.

To accomplish these tasks, it is necessary to distribute the many types of adaptation into subsets according to their classification characteristics, based on identifying the most essential features inherent in them, distinguishing them from each other. Classification is a necessary component of the knowledge of the phenomenon of adaptation.

According to the results of the technological audit of the subject area of adaptation (complexity, uncertainty, dynamism, instability), classification of the types of essential attributes of enterprise adaptation is carried out. On the basis of a questionnaire survey of managers and key specialists of 37 retail enterprises, a list of problems of adaptation to the external environment is determined. The generalization of the results of the survey allows to expand the existing classification features of the adaptation of the enterprise by introducing additional ones, namely:

- according to the level and degree of planning (adaptation is planned when the enterprise has an adaptation model that is implemented according to the plan; spontaneous adaptation, which is carried out spontaneously depending on the specific situation);
 - if necessary, investment support (capital-intensive adaptation, which requires investment support for full completion; non-capital-intensive adaptation, which occurs at the expense of the current expenses of the enterprise);
 - according to the degree of cost recovery (adaptation costs, when there is a probability that the adaptation will not pay off or will not bring profit; profitable adaptation, which indicates possible profit as a result of adaptation to changes in the external environment).
- Table 1 shows the results of systematization of classification characteristics of enterprise adaptation.

It should be noted that the adaptation potential of enterprises in various spheres of economic activity has certain specific features. Existing approaches to the classification of specific manifestations of adaptation are generally of a general nature and do not take into account the characteristic sectoral features of the activities of enterprises in certain spheres of economic activity.

The specifics of the retail industry are determined by the following characteristics [19]:

- retailers, as a rule, sell products made by others, and as a result can't benefit from the exclusivity of their product range;
- trade faster than other sectors of the economy responds to changes in the consumer market;
- retailers directly interact with end users.

Table 1

Systematization of classification features of enterprise adaptation

No.	Classification feature	Specific manifestations of the enterprise adaptation
1	By the scope of implementation [1, 4]	– economic; – organizational and managerial; – technical and technological; – social and labor; – complex; – local
2	By the functional sphere [2, 5]	– production; – marketing; – logistic; – financial; – scientific and technical; – staff adaptation
3	By the time characteristic [6, 7]	– permanent; – cyclic; – periodic; – simultaneous; – long-term; – short-term; – operational; – strategic; – tactical
4	By the method of action [9]	– static; – dynamic
5	By the coverage [11, 12]	– complex; – local
6	By the degree and efficiency of use of the means of production [9]	– intense; – extensive; – integrated
7	By the nature of the parameters change [14]	– parametric; – resource; – algorithmic; – structural
8	By the type of adaptive response [1]	– elastic; – flexible; – plastic
9	By control level [3]	– highest management level; – medium management level; – lower management level
10	By means of adaptation [5]	– quantitative; – quality; – modulation
11	By the environmental factors [7]	– adaptation to innovations; – adaptation to changing market conditions; – adaptation to socio-economic conditions; – adaptation to political conditions
12	By the level of adaptation [13]	– primary; – secondary
13	By the degree of predictability of changes in the environment [15]	– forced; – planned; – precautionary
14	By the final result [14]	– aimed at survival; – aims to maintain a stable state; – aimed at sustainable development; – constructive; – destructive
15	By the nature of the changes made [16, 17]	– passive; – active; – preventive; – compensatory
16	If necessary, investment support*	– capital-intensive; – not capital-intensive
17	By the degree of payback*	– expensive; – profitable
18	By the planning level*	– planned; – spontaneous

Note: * highlighted by authors

In this regard, the adaptation potential of a retail enterprise is quite sensitive both to the variability of input resources, and the requirements and demands of consumers, which characterizes its differences from enterprises in other sectors of the economy. That is why managing the adaptation potential of a retailer is characterized by a high level of dynamism, which must take into account all the parameters of its functioning. Considering this, the retail enterprise classification system should reflect the deep patterns in the development of objective reality – a multifaceted process of adaptation.

Taking into account the need to adapt a retailer to the increasing demands and demands of consumers, let's believe that when forming an adaptation policy, the focus should be on the 4P marketing mix (product, price, place of sale, promotion) [20]. These elements of the 4P marketing mix should be taken into account when implementing a marketing adaptation of a retailer. The «Product» element makes it possible to find the answer to the question «How to adapt the product range to meet the requirements of the target audience?» The «Price» element helps to identify key aspects of price adjustment to ensure the adaptation of the price of goods sold by the retailer to the real incomes of the population. Adaptation of the «Place of Sale» element helps to form adaptive models of procurement and product distribution. And the element «Promotion» allows to answer the question «How to adapt the atmosphere of a retail outlet (store) to increase consumer loyalty and their awareness of the product?»

Considering this, at a retail outlet, it is advisable to single out such specific types of marketing adaptation as: commodity, price, communication, spatial. Key characteristics of the selected types of adaptation of the retail enterprise are shown in Fig. 1.

Elements of the 4P marketing mix	Type of marketing adaptation	Key features
Product	Commodity	It is aimed at changing approaches to the formation of inventories and, accordingly, the structure and volume of the range of goods depending on the requirements and demands of consumers, changing approaches to quality control of goods
Price	Pricing	It is aimed at changing the pricing policy in accordance with changes in real incomes of consumers and their consumer preferences
Place	Spatial	It is aimed at improving the quality of the logistics service for consumers of a commercial enterprise and involves changing the atmosphere of the store, improving the conditions for displaying goods and the rules for displaying, placing departments and various groups of goods
Promotion	Communication	Aimed at changing the means of communication and product communications to the consumer. Provides for a change in approaches to the preparation and placement of promotional materials. Basic requirements for the implementation of communication adaptation: – studies should be conducted on the life style and values of the target group of consumers; – in communication should be used available to the consumer semantic schemes; – communication must be consistent and gradually create a holistic image of the product

Fig. 1. Specific types of marketing adaptation of the retail enterprise (developed on the basis of data [21, 22])

Such an approach to the classification of types of adaptation of a retailer will allow to positively adapt to the requirements and demands of the consumer and create a positive consumer mood. This, in turn, will contribute to the growth of the main resulting indicators – turnover and profits.

7. SWOT analysis of research results

Strengths. The strengths lie is the fact that the improved classification of specific manifestations of the adaptation of a retailer through the introduction of additional ones (in terms of the level and degree of planning, investment support, and in the degree of recoupage of costs):

- is the basis for assessing the adaptive capacity and choosing the optimal type of adaptive response of business entities in the field of trade;
- creates a basis for the discovery of new opportunities to improve competitiveness.

Focusing the attention of management and managers of retail enterprises on commodity, price, communication and spatial types of marketing adaptation will allow:

- to adapt key trade and operational processes with the requirements and demands of the consumer;
- to maximize the volume of trade and profits.

Weaknesses. The weak side of the proposed approach to the systematization of types of adaptation potential is the complexity of assessing each of them. It is necessary to systematically update the information available to the company (or person) about a wide range of environmental factors in order to implement a timely adaptive response to their changes.

Opportunities. It should be noted that in the future it is necessary to assess the level of the adaptation potential of the retailer and to determine the main directions of its optimization, which is possible on the basis of improving the methodological tools of this assessment. Methodological tools can be upgraded, including quantitative and qualitative indicators for assessing the adaptive capacity, taking into account the sectoral specifics of trade enterprises.

Threats. The threats to the proposed approach to structuring the adaptation potential of a retailer can be attributed to the fact that the high amplitude of changes in environmental factors, the increasing demands of consumers, the high level of competition in the field of trade necessitate the identification of new types of adaptation potential.

8. Conclusions

1. The analysis of existing approaches to the classification of types of adaptation of the enterprise has been carried out and systematized them according to the main criteria:
 - by the scope of implementation;
 - by the functional area;

- by the time characteristic;
- by the way of action;
- by the degree of coverage;
- by the degree and efficiency of use of the means of production;
- by the nature of the change parameters;
- by the type of adaptive response;
- by the level of management;
- by the means of adaptation;
- by the environmental factors;
- by the level of adaptation;
- by the degree of predictability of environmental changes;
- by the final result;
- by the nature of the changes that are made.

Introduced additional classification features of the adaptation of the enterprise:

- if necessary, investment support;
- by the degree of recoument of expenses;
- by the level of planning.

2. The classification of specific manifestations of the adaptation of a retailer has been improved by introducing additional:

- by the level and degree of planning (planned, spontaneous);
- by the investment support (capital-intensive, non-capital-intensive);
- by the degree of recoument of costs (cost, income).

3. Specific types of marketing adaptation of a retail enterprise (commodity, price, communication, spatial) have been proposed and characterized. Accounting for the identified types of adaptation creates an opportunity to increase the competitiveness of a retailer by maintaining the balance of compliance of internal parameters with the requirements and needs of consumers.

The practical significance of the research results is identification of the main key accents that should be taken into account by the trading enterprise in the formation of adaptation policies.

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